

METHODS FOR ASSESSING ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY IN RESIDENTIAL CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract. *The article examines the acceleration of urbanization processes at the global and national levels, as well as issues related to natural population growth in the republic, the increasing demand for housing, housing provision, and the greening of housing construction. It also discusses environmental safety in housing construction, the introduction of certification systems and international green standards, and the determination of an average coefficient for assessing the share of commissioned housing according to its environmental performance level. In addition, the article proposes future methods for the economic assessment of the quality of environmentally friendly housing construction.*

Keywords: *urbanization, environmental safety, eco-friendly housing, greening, green standards, green certification, ecological level, sustainable housing.*

Introduction

In the modern world, ecological construction, particularly housing construction, is of great importance because it makes it possible to reduce the negative impact of human activity on the environment. Eco-friendly housing and infrastructure facilities help reduce greenhouse gas emissions, decrease the consumption of energy, water, and other resources, and improve air quality in cities. In addition, ecological housing construction contributes to creating healthy and comfortable conditions for people to live and work. Therefore, the development of ecological housing construction is an important step toward sustainable development and helps preserve natural resources for future generations.

It should be noted that almost half of the world's population lives in cities, and forecasts indicate that by 2030, approximately 75% of the population will become urban residents [1]. According to reports by the Eurasian Development Bank, by 2035, the urban population in Central Asia is expected to increase from 39 million to 45 million people. The main reason for this is internal migration. Due to low incomes, the labor force is moving from rural areas to cities. The growth of the urban population, in turn, requires increased investment in engineering projects, including energy and water supply, heat supply, transport, and other sectors; social infrastructure, such as a comfortable living environment; and digital management technologies. Thus, the demand for housing will continue to increase, and at the same time, the impact on the environment will also intensify [2].

The modernization and construction of urban infrastructure is a systemic problem, comparable in importance to the effective management of water and energy resources in the region. This is because insufficiently developed infrastructure seriously limits the growth of production capacity, the economy, and social welfare, while also making it more difficult to manage various risks, including environmental risks. In large cities, unregulated construction is often observed.

The consequences of such urbanization include increased pressure on urban labor markets, the deterioration of engineering infrastructure, climate change, natural disasters, and a high level of vulnerability to environmental threats. At the same time, the construction sector, particularly industrial and residential construction, plays an important role in combating the problem of climate change.

Methodology

This study uses a theoretical-analytical and economic-assessment approach to examine the environmental quality of residential construction. The analysis is based on statistical data on housing construction and housing demand in Uzbekistan, regulatory documents on green construction, and international green certification systems. In particular, the study considers the requirements of ShNQ 2.07.05-19, “Green Construction. Residential and Public Buildings. Rating System for Assessing the Sustainability of the Living Environment,” as the national regulatory basis for assessing the sustainability of residential and public buildings.

To assess the ecological level of commissioned housing, the study proposes the use of an average coefficient that reflects the share of housing according to its environmental quality level. The coefficient is calculated by comparing the volume and unit cost of housing belonging to a particular ecological level with the total commissioned housing volume and the unit cost of housing with the maximum permissible ecological level:

$$\mathbf{Kek} = (\mathbf{FTUJ}_i \times \mathbf{N}_i) / (\mathbf{FTUJum} \times \mathbf{Nech})$$

where **Kek** is the average coefficient of the ecological level of commissioned housing; **FTUJ_i** is the volume of commissioned housing belonging to the *i*-th ecological level, measured in square meters; **N_i** is the price of 1 m² of housing belonging to the *i*-th ecological level, measured in thousand soums; **FTUJum** is the total volume of commissioned housing, measured in square meters; and **Nech** is the price of 1 m² of housing with the maximum permissible ecological level, measured in thousand soums.

In addition, the study proposes four groups of methods for the future economic assessment of ecological housing construction quality: general methods applied at the design stage; specific methods applied during the operation stage; full economic assessment methods that consider all characteristics of ecological quality; and simplified economic assessment methods that consider selected ecological quality indicators only.

Results

If we look at the following statistical data related to housing construction, one of the driving sectors in the republic, and the provision of housing for the population, we can see that in 2025, 106.5 thousand new apartments were commissioned in Uzbekistan. This is a historically high figure. However, the construction sector is still not developing in line with the country’s demographic growth rate. As 200 thousand new families are formed every year, the housing shortage has exceeded 90 thousand apartments. However, this figure is 28.5 thousand fewer than the target set for 2025, which was 135 thousand apartments. Overall, 1,936 residential buildings were constructed last year, which is almost 1.5 times higher than the figure recorded in 2019, when 1,324 buildings were constructed [3].

According to Sh. Qudbiyev, Chairman of the National Committee for Urbanization and Sustainable Development of the Housing Market [3], despite record-high construction volumes, the current pace does not fully meet the natural population growth. In order to increase the housing area per person from 18.9 square meters to 23 square meters by 2040, it is necessary to significantly

expand construction volumes. Moreover, to reach the level of 23 square meters of housing space per person, the country needs to achieve a construction rate of 280 thousand apartments per year by 2040.

Discussion

The ecologization of housing construction is carried out in order to protect the environment and safeguard human health. More specifically, public health is closely connected with the quality of housing, which is influenced by the materials and technologies used in construction, the characteristics of the soil beneath buildings, motorization, urbanization, and other factors. Therefore, the level of protection or safety a person feels in their own home should not be understood narrowly as merely compliance with hygienic standards. Rather, in a broader sense, ensuring the environmental safety of housing means a set of measures aimed at providing people with a certain level of ecological protection based on established standards during the production, construction, and operation of the modern living environment.

Environmental safety in construction refers to a set of natural, social, technical, engineering, and other conditions that ensure ecological balance in nature and protect the environment and human beings from the harmful effects of unfavorable factors arising from anthropogenic impact, such as construction [4].

It is particularly important to note that, at present, the importance of environmental safety in housing construction is increasing in the country. This is related to the growth of the urban population and the expansion of commercial and industrial activities. In addition, large cities concentrate energy and resource consumption, generate enormous amounts of waste, and place excessive pressure on both artificial and natural systems. Managing these systems and regulating their functions is becoming increasingly difficult. This situation is further complicated by the construction of new residential areas and the rapid growth of the urban population. As a result, the damage caused to the environment and the costs of protecting it reach such a scale that they threaten human health and worsen living conditions.

It should be noted that, when assessing the quality of the environment in large cities at the master-plan level, conducting ecological assessments of housing construction, developing specific projects, and planning environmental protection and rational use of natural resources at the scale of the city and its surrounding areas, special attention must be paid to their condition.

Environmental safety is important at the stages of constructing, operating, and demolishing or liquidating residential and other buildings. Engineering and ecological studies in construction are conducted to assess the current state of the environment and to forecast its possible changes under the influence of anthropogenic pressure. Their purpose is to prevent, reduce, or eliminate harmful and undesirable environmental consequences, as well as related social, economic, and other impacts, while preserving favorable living conditions for the population [4].

Thus, at present, the development and scientific justification of methods for the economic assessment of the quality of ecological housing construction are becoming increasingly relevant. The application of such methods should become a mandatory requirement in the ecological expert assessment of newly constructed residential buildings. It should be emphasized that, so far, there is no stable and unified assessment system recognized at the international level. However, from the perspective of quality of life and the sustainable development of territories, there is a strong need for such an assessment system that accurately reflects the condition of newly commissioned residential housing.

In developed countries, in order to construct green buildings and sustainable territories, green certification systems have been adopted for assessing ecological housing facilities. These systems include a set of criteria and requirements. In turn, they stimulate the active development of an innovative segment of the construction market, namely the market for green housing construction. At the same time, a relevant system of measures is required to ensure the reproduction and wider implementation of this type of green building by developers, end users, other relevant participants in the green construction market, and business partners, as well as to provide state support at all stages of the building life cycle.

In housing construction, projects are constantly improved and adapted to local conditions. They also meet all needs related to the economic, social, and climatic conditions of a particular territory by making the most effective use of local resources. Every society has its own traditions of housing construction, as a result of which it is possible to speak about architecture that reflects distinctive construction methods and ways of life. However, local construction culture does not remain unchanged. It develops in close connection with the progress of society. This can be explained by the development of political, economic, socio-humanitarian, spiritual, educational, and cultural relations between countries at various levels, as well as by the emergence of new knowledge and skills, construction techniques, technologies and methods, construction materials, products, and structures.

In the international community, the issue of green standards began to be discussed at the end of the last century. In some developed countries, the first green construction standards were developed, and relevant government policies in this area emerged.

It should be noted that in the United Kingdom, the BREEAM rating system for green buildings, officially known as the BRE Environmental Assessment Method, was developed, while in the United States, the LEED eco-certification system, Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design, was introduced. At the beginning of the 2000s, the German Sustainable Building Council, DGNB, developed new standards that analyze the future environmental sustainability of a building by taking into account its functional capabilities over the next 50 years. In the Russian Federation, in 2022, two new green construction standards were developed as part of the development of the national real estate assessment system: GOST R, intended for the assessment of apartment buildings, and KLEVER, intended for commercial and non-commercial real estate facilities. These standards began operating simultaneously. The BREEAM, LEED, and DGNB rating systems have one common goal: to conserve resources and reduce the negative impact of the created artificial human living environment on the natural environment and human health. Therefore, most green standards pay particular attention to socio-economic factors and energy efficiency indicators. At the beginning of the new millennium, an intergovernmental network organization uniting similar councils around the world, the World Green Building Council, or WorldGBC, was established. Every year, this Council holds the World Congress on Green Building in Canada, where its headquarters is located [5].

To date, the standards that have been operating successfully can be adapted to the legislative requirements of almost any country. Therefore, many green construction standards of international significance have now been adapted in many other countries as well. It should be noted that ShNQ 2.07.05-19, **“Green Construction. Residential and Public Buildings. Rating System for Assessing the Sustainability of the Living Environment”** [6], has been approved in the republic. This document establishes a rating system for assessing the sustainability of the human living environment, which meets the objectives of satisfying the needs of the present

generation for a comfortable living environment and fulfilling state functions through the use of residential buildings and public facilities without reducing the level of such opportunities.

The requirements of this rating system are aimed at reducing the consumption of energy resources while ensuring a comfortable living environment for people and sufficient economic profitability of architectural, structural, and engineering solutions; promoting the use of non-traditional, renewable, and secondary energy resources; ensuring the rational use of water; and reducing the harmful impact on the environment during the construction and operation of buildings.

In this regard, it would be appropriate to use the following average coefficient, which determines the “**environmental cleanliness**” [7] of housing being commissioned, that is, the share of its ecological level here:

$$K_{ek} = \frac{\sum (FTUJ_i \cdot N_i)}{FTUJ_{um} \cdot N_{ech}}$$

K_{ek} - the average coefficient of the ecological level of housing being commissioned;

FTUJ_i - the volume of housing being commissioned that belongs to the *i*-th type of ecological level, m²;

N_i - the price of 1 m² of housing belonging to the *i*-th type of ecological level, thousand soums;

FTUJ_{um} - the total volume of housing being commissioned, m²;

N_{ech} - the price of 1 m² of housing with the maximum permissible limit of the ecological level, thousand soums.

In this case, every building being standardized should be considered in the process of developing standards not only as a production object, but also as a consumption object. This is because the quality indicators of each type of building depend not only on the quality of the materials and components used, but also, in turn, influence the overall quality and economic efficiency of the building.

In ecological housing construction, this approach is of particular importance. This is explained by the social and economic significance of such buildings, their long service life, the high costs of construction and operation, and their impact on people’s living and working conditions, as well as on the efficiency of capital investments.

Conclusion

In the future, the following methods may be used for the economic assessment of the quality of ecological housing construction:

- general methods, which are applied at the design stage of a residential building and make it possible to assess the ecological quality of the building in the future;
- specific methods, which are applied at the stage of building operation and serve to assess the environmental safety of the living environment;
- full economic assessment methods, which take into account all characteristics describing the ecological quality of a residential building;
- simplified economic assessment methods, which take into account only certain characteristics describing ecological quality.

The methods presented above make it possible to carry out a comprehensive quantitative assessment of the integral indicator of the quality of ecological housing construction. In this case, the number of characteristics describing the ecological quality of a residential building is selected

in such a way that they can express the ecological quality of any residential building with sufficient completeness.

In general, the existing problems in traditional housing construction emphasize the need to shift toward ecological construction, which takes environmental impact into account, uses energy-saving materials and technologies, and helps reduce negative effects on nature.

Ecological housing construction includes the use of environmentally friendly materials, energy efficiency and alternative energy sources, as well as the conservation of natural resources and rational land use.

First of all, the use of environmentally friendly materials means selecting materials that have minimal impact on the environment during extraction, production, application, and disposal. These include natural and renewable materials such as wood, clay, and straw, as well as environmentally friendly synthetic materials made from recycled waste.

Secondly, energy efficiency and the use of alternative energy sources include designing buildings with reduced energy consumption in mind and using energy-saving technologies and systems for heating, cooling, and lighting. It is also important to use alternative energy sources such as solar, wind, or geothermal energy.

Thirdly, the conservation of natural resources and rational land use include taking ecological factors into account in design and construction processes, reducing land use, preserving biodiversity, protecting water resources, and using land rationally for infrastructure.

In addition, it is worth noting that the main methods of ecological housing construction include the use of green roofs and walls, solar panels and rainwater harvesting systems, as well as the use of recycled and renewable materials.

Recommendations

The main directions and methods identified above regarding the need to transition to ecological housing construction help reduce negative impacts on the environment, improve the energy efficiency of residential buildings and infrastructure, and ensure the efficient and sustainable use of natural resources.

Overall, ecological housing construction is one of the important areas of the modern construction sector and serves to improve people's quality of life and develop sustainable cities. The importance of this field is determined by the reduction of energy consumption, the use of renewable energy sources, the improvement of air and water quality, and the reduction of the carbon footprint. It should be noted that, in the context of rapidly developing cities and a growing population, ecological housing construction will become an integral part of the construction sector of the future. Moreover, the introduction of ecological technologies and approaches into construction processes will closely contribute to the creation of a sustainable and healthy living environment.

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